

EFFECTS OF CROSSWORDS AND WORD SEARCH TEACHING STRATEGIES ON BIOLOGY STUDENTS' INTEREST AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT ON HUMAN SKELETAL SYSTEM IN CALABAR SOUTH, CROSS RIVER STATE

BY

EKON, Esther Etop¹, UDOH, Nsimeneabasi Michael², UDO, Mmedara Joseph³
ODIGIRI, Emmanuel Junior⁴, WILLIAMS, Idongesit Sylvanus⁵ and AKPAN,
Ndifreke Celetine⁶

^{1,3,4}Department of Biology Education, University of Calabar, Calabar

^{2,5,6}Department of Science Education, University of Uyo, Uyo.

Email: nismeneabasimudo@uniuyo.edu.ng

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Abstract

The study was on the effect of crosswords and word search teaching strategies on students' interest and academic achievement in Calabar South L. G. A. in Cross River State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study employed a non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design. The population of the study was 5,237 Senior Secondary School two (SSS2) students and the sample size comprised 172 senior secondary one (SS1) students from 3 co-educational schools. Two instruments namely, Biology-students' Interest Inventory (BII) and Biology Achievement Test (BAT) were employed in the study and their reliability coefficients were 0.83 and 0.78 respectively indicating that both instruments were sufficiently reliable for data collection. Data were collected by administering the two instruments before and after treatment respectively. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while ANCOVA was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that there were significant differences among the mean interest and academic achievement scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies. There were no significant differences found between the mean interest and academic achievement scores of male and female Biology students. However, it was recommended among others, that Biology teachers should make use of crosswords and word search teaching strategies in the teaching of human skeletal system. Parents and Biology teachers should encourage both male and female students towards excellence in Biology since they can benefit equally from science instructions depending on the involvement of an individual student.

Keywords: Interest, Academic achievement, Human Skeletal System, Crosswords, Word search.

Introduction

Education is an important aspect of every nation especially in developing countries such as Nigeria. Udoh *et al.* (2024) opined that true education is that which learners are equipped with the ability to perceive accurately, think clearly and act effectively. This equipping is accomplished via the three domains in education- cognitive, affective and psychomotor. According to Ottman (2023), education is said to be effective when learners acquire knowledge, develop skills and adopt values in order to make a difference in the society but the case is different in the educational system in Nigeria. This is evidenced in the students' performance in both internal and external examinations like West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National

Examinations Council (NECO) (Udoh & Ndirika, 2025). The effective implementation of any curriculum depends on a large extent the method used in disseminating information or knowledge to the students' understanding in science subjects like Biology.

Biology is regarded as the scientific study of organisms. Ottman (2023) opined that Biology is a branch of science that deals with the study of living organisms and their interrelationship with their environments. Biology is a useful science with several application in the society, Biology helps to understand ourselves, our environments and provides us with the knowledge of how our crops and domestic animals can thrive better (Udoh & Ndirika, 2025). In Nigeria, Biology is one of the core subjects of the curriculum

as reflected in the 6th edition of Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013). Despite all these gains, students still perform poorly in West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National examination Council (NECO) examinations. According to Farber (2023), the West African Examination Council's Chief Examiners' yearly reports (2018-2023) have shown a downward trend in the performance of students in science subjects including Biology. Arends and Abdullahi (2024) noted that several research reports revealed that the performance of students in this subject at secondary school level has been on the decline in both internal and external examinations due to the use of conventional teaching method by most Biology teachers.

Conventional teaching method is a teacher-centred approach and has been proven to be ineffective in students' understanding of concepts; Ekwueme *et al.* (2015) confirmed that teachers using conventional methods spoon-feed learners and so do not challenge them to discover new methods of tackling problems. Ekon and Udoh (2021) posited that conventional method of instruction present science learning as a mental process where facts are to be memorized rather than a set of principles for application in the outside world. Considering the nature of Biology as a subject that involved natural phenomena and activity-based concepts, there is a need to have a pedagogical shift to a student-centred approach that enhances interest and achievement of students and this can be implored with innovative strategies which are activity-oriented, interactive and students-centred strategy such as gamification.

Gamification is the process of adding games or game-like elements to a task. Selcuk and Keshin (2024) defined gamification as an educational approach where games (digital and analogue) are used in order to engage students in interactive and immersive experiences designed to teach specific concepts, skills or subjects. This implies the use of games to encourage participation and capture the interest and academic

achievement of an individual. In education, gamification can be explored to raise students' interest and enhance critical thinking skills, particularly in science subjects such as Biology. Faber (2023) stated that gamification is the use of game design elements in non-game context, meaning when games are introduced in a non-game context like schools, it can enhance learners' critical thinking skills making the learning of Biology concepts easier and retention of concepts better. Zicherman and Cunningham (2021) posited that gamification is using game-based thinking and game-related functions to help users solve problems and attract their interest. This interest on the part of the learners can help shift learning from a teacher-centred approach to a student-centred approach. What is learnt through games tends to be retained better by students due to the interactive nature and the learning experiences in a conducive learning environment (Ekon & Udoh, 2021). There are several games like digital games, scrabble, wheel spin, puzzles and crosswords that may be employed for better academic achievement. For the purpose of this paper, the researchers investigated the incorporation of game-based activities into classroom learning activities to enhance students' interest and academic achievement using Crosswords and Word search.

Crosswords and word search are two popular games that can be used as a form of gamification in Biology learning environments (Selcuk and Keskin, 2024). Crossword puzzles consist of grid of squares with clues for filling in the words horizontally and vertically. Scrabble on the other is a board game where players form words from letter tiles and score points based on the length of words. Both games require a good knowledge of the language and subject and a strategic mind to find the best words possible (Farber, 2023). According to Zichermann and Cunningham (2021), crosswords and scrabble games can enhance students' vocabulary, spellings and motivate them to learn more about Biology.

Scrabble games can enhance students' vocabulary, spellings and motivate them to learn more about biology. For instance, a crossword game can have clues such as the process of cell division or the molecule that carries genetic information and students have to fill in the blank spaces with the correct words while a Scrabble game can have tiles with letters and symbols that represent biological concepts such as 'C' for carbon or 'A' for adenine and students have to form words that are valid in Biology such as DNA or ENZYMES. Crossword, and wordsearch can be played individually or with others, online or offline can be customised according to the level or class of study. These games offer many benefits for the brain such as improving memory, concentration and problem-solving abilities. Farber (2023) found a significantly higher achievement scores than their counterparts in the control group when taught with gamification. Selcuk and Keskin (2024) found no significant difference on students' interest when taught science concepts and it can be taught to both gender.

Gender refers to the characteristics of women, men, girls and boys that are socially constructed. These include norms, behaviours and roles associated with being a woman, man, girl or boy, as well as relationships with each other (Anidu & Udoh, 2021). It is either of the two sexes (male and female), especially when considered with reference to biological, social and cultural differences. Gender issue in education with academic achievement and retention have become very important issue among researchers. Some research works have shown contradicting evidences in students' academic achievement in science due to gender. For instance, Udo (2023); Ottman (2023) found out that there is no significant influence in the academic achievement of male and female Biology students but Udoh et al, (2024) reported that there are significant gender differences in students' academic achievement and retention in sciences. Sambo and Sunday

(2024) observed that male students achieved and retained significantly better than their female counterparts in mathematics when taught using iconic models. Since students may forget the topic of the lesson but will not forget the illustrations used in demonstrating the exercise, the use of games as instructional strategy could enhance students' interest, (Udoh & Ndirika, 2025).

Students' interests refer to an attitude expressing concentration, attention and persistence of activity towards a particular subject. Students' interests play an important role in the teaching/learning processes and it is used to designate what attracts an individual to various objects, persons, course and activities within the person's environment. Udoh and Ndirika (2025) opined that when a learning task is set before the students, the aptness in responding to the set learning task is centrally controlled by interest. Udo (2023) added that in the field of education, interest has been the pivot that enables a student to be actively involved in any course of study. Udoh et al, (2020) stated that the extent to which a student is interested in a particular course of study is indicated by the student's active participation in the study of the subject with resultant good performance in same. Student's interest is what every teacher in any field of study strives to obtain in order to transfer learning to the learners. Udoh (2021) found a significant difference in the interest of Biology students on genetics because interest promotes intrinsic motivation which has been shown to drive and sustain students' engagement in a particular task. She added that the extent to which the student is interested in a particular course of study is indicated by active participation in the study with good performance. Udoh and Ndirika (2025) found no significant difference on students' interest when taught science concepts. Udoh (2021) added that students who have interest in any concept taught do better than those with little or no interest which could determine students' academic achievement.

Academic achievement is the degree or level of success gained at the conclusion of educational endeavours. It is the extent to which students have achieved educational goals. Sambo and Sunday (2024) described academic achievement as the scholastic standing of a student at a given moment, which states individual abilities. Students' academic achievement can be explained in the form of grades obtained from tests or examinations on subjects taken. Effiong (2023) ascertain that numerous factors contribute or militate against improved academic achievement of students in schools and some of these factors include lack of appropriate or suitable teaching methods. Arends and Abdullahi (2024) found that gamification has been found to have a significant impact on Biology education and have positive effect on students' achievement. Udo (2023) found no significant difference between two gamification approaches used in the learning process. Studies by Selcuk and Keskin (2024) show that only few studies have examined the effects of crossword and word search within the context of Biology learning, again the knowledge of how to gamify an activity in the class are limited; thus, the present study to fill the existing gap.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study.

1. What is the difference in the mean interest scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies?
2. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies

Research Method

A word search contained hidden skeletal terms that learners must find in a word search worksheet. Examples of words such as Skullm, Cranium, Rib, Sternum, Vertebrae, Pelvis, Femur, Tibia, Fibula, Humerus, Radius, Ulna, Patella. They later discussed the location and function of each bone found and this help students become familiar with skeletal vocabulary and improves observation and concentration skills. In crossword, students answered clues related to bones and skeletal functions. Teacher distributed crossword puzzle containing clues, allows students to complete it individually and in groups. Teacher reviews answers and provide corrections

The study adopted a non-randomized pretest-posttest control group of the quasi-experimental design specifically, pre-test, post-test control group quasi experimental design was used for the study. Two research questions guided the study. The population of the study comprised all the Senior Secondary one (SS1) Biology students in the study area in 2024/2025 academic session. A total number of one hundred and seventy-two (172) SS1 students formed the study sample. Two instruments, namely, Biology Students' Interest Inventory (BSII) and Biology Achievement Test (BAT) developed by the researchers were used for data collection. The BSII questionnaire was made up of 25 statements and was scored using the 4-point Likert type scale. The BAT consisted of 30 multiple test questions on the concept-Human skeletal system. These test items were scored using pre-

determined marking guide. These two instruments underwent face and content validity and reliability coefficient established using Richard kuderson (KR-20) and Cronbach alpha as 0.83 and 0.78 respectively.

Simple random sampling technique was used to select three schools out of the 15 government-owned coeducational schools in the study area. This means that each school was randomly assigned to either control or experimental groups. The Biology teachers in the experimental groups received prior pedagogical training on how to use crossword and word search in the process of teaching the concept- human skeletal system, the training lasted for 2 days. The trained teacher in the experimental groups taught the lesson using the researchers’ note of lesson, the prepared crossword and word search, while the control group students were the

same lesson conventionally by their teacher who received no form of training from the researchers. Prior to treatment, the students in the three groups were pre-tested using BAT. This was done to determine the students’ knowledge on the concept, the human skeletal system. After the treatment, a post-test was administered on the students (reshuffled pre-test). The data obtained from the tests administered were analyzed using mean score, standard deviation and Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA).

Results

Research question one: What is the difference in the mean interest scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies?

The results of these analyses are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-interest and Post- interest Scores of Students taught Human Skeletal System Grouped by Teaching Strategies

Teaching Strategies	Pre-interest		Post- interest		Mean Difference	
	N	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}		SD
Wordsearch	57	11.67	2.58	22.32	3.94	10.65
Crossword	61	11.36	1.95	22.02	3.95	10.66
Conventional	54	11.02	1.87	18.69	3.35	7.67

Results in Table 1 show the mean difference scores of students taught the concept of taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies as 10.65, 10.66 and 7.67 respectively. Comparing the mean difference scores of the three groups, it indicates that crossword with mean difference score of 10.66 was the highest in enhancing students’ interest, followed by wordsearch with mean

difference score of 10.65. The use of conventional teaching strategy was the least with mean difference score of 7.67 in enhancing students’ interest in human skeletal system.

Research question two: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies? The results of these analyses are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-test and Post-post Scores of Students taught Human Skeletal System Grouped by Teaching Strategies

Teaching Strategies	Pre-test		Post- test		Mean Difference
	N	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	

Wordsearch	57	12.93	2.82	29.30	4.96	16.37
Crossword	61	11.80	2.09	28.15	4.06	16.35
Conventional	54	10.91	1.84	22.59	5.13	11.68

Results in Table 2 show the mean difference scores of students taught the concept of taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies as 16.37, 16.35 and 11.68 respectively. Comparing the mean difference scores of the three groups, it indicates that wordsearch with mean difference score of 16.37 was the highest in enhancing students' achievement, followed by crossword with mean difference score of 16.35. The use of

conventional teaching strategy was the least with mean difference score of 11.68 in enhancing students' achievement in human skeletal system.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies. The results of these analyses are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Post-interest Scores Classified by Teaching Strategies with Pre-interest Scores as Covariate

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value
Corrected Model	2670.089 ^a	3	890.030	62.33	.00*
Intercept	1987.647	1	1987.647	139.19	.00*
Pre-interest	6.036	1	6.036	.42	.51 ^{NS}
Strategies	2606.475	2	1303.238	91.26	.00*
Error	2398.911	168	14.279		
Total	70472.000	172			
Corrected Total	5069.000	171			

^{NS} = Not significant at .05 level of significance; * = Significant at .05 level of significance

Results in Table 3 show that the analysis of covariate (pre-interest scores) of the three groups of students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies is significant since the calculated F-value (.42) having a calculated p-value (.51) is greater than the significant level (.05), indicating that the mean of the three groups were statistically equivalent. The table also shows that the calculated F-value (91.26) having a

calculated p-value (.00) of the main effect of teaching strategies is less than the significant level (.05), therefore, the null hypothesis one is rejected. This implies that there exists a significant difference among the interest scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies. In order to determine the direction of significance, the scores were subjected to post hoc analysis as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: LSD (Least Square Difference) Post hoc Analysis of Students' Post-interest Grouped by Teaching Strategies with Pre-interest as Covariate

(I) Strategies	(J) Strategies	Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig ^b
Wordsearch	Crossword	.273	.697	.69 ^{NS}
	Conventional	8.574*	.723	.00*
Crossword	Wordsearch	-.273	.697	.69 ^{NS}
	Conventional	8.301*	.708	.00*
Conventional	Wordsearch	-8.574*	.723	.00*
	Crossword	-8.301*	.708	.00*

^{NS} = Not significant at .05 level of significance; * = Significant at .05 level of significance

Table 4 shows the post hoc analysis scores of students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies. Students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies had a significantly higher interest when compared with those taught using conventional teaching strategy. A non-significant difference existed between the interest scores of students

taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies. The results of these analyses are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Post-test Scores Classified by Teaching Strategies with Pre-test Scores as Covariate

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value
Corrected Model	3903.725 ^a	3	1301.242	59.22	.00*
Intercept	2908.180	1	2908.180	132.36	.00*
Pre-test	77.509	1	77.509	3.52	.06 ^{NS}
Strategies	3201.540	2	1600.770	72.85	.00*
Error	3691.130	168	21.971		
Total	119693.000	172			
Corrected Total	7594.855	171			

^{NS} = Not significant at .05 level of significance; * = Significant at .05 level of significance

Results in Table 5 show that the analysis of covariate (pre-test scores) of the three groups of students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies is not significant since the calculated F-value (3.52) having a calculated p-value (.06) is greater than the significant level (.05), indicating that the mean of the three groups were statistically equivalent. The table also shows that the calculated F-value (72.85) having a calculated p-value (.00) of the main

effect of teaching strategies is less than the significant level (.05), therefore, the null hypothesis one is rejected. This implies that there exists a significant difference among the achievement scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies. In order to determine the direction of significance, the scores were subjected to post hoc analysis as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: LSD (Least Square Difference) Post hoc Analysis of Students' Post-test Grouped by Teaching Strategies with Pre-test as Covariate

(I) Strategies	(J) Strategies	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b
Wordsearch	Crossword	.819	.88	.35 ^{NS}
	Conventional	10.109*	.94	.00*
Crossword	Wordsearch	-.819	.88	.35 ^{NS}
	Conventional	9.291*	.88	.00*
Conventional	Wordsearch	-10.109*	.94	.00*
	Crossword	-9.291*	.88	.00*

^{NS} = Not significant at .05 level of significance; * = Significant at .05 level of significance

Table 6 shows the post hoc analysis scores of students taught human skeletal using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies. Students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies had a significantly higher achievement when compared with those taught using conventional teaching strategy. A non-significant difference existed between the achievement scores of students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on the difference among the mean interest scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies indicated a significant difference. Students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies had a significantly higher interest when compared with those taught using conventional teaching strategy. A non-significant difference existed among the interest mean scores of Biology students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies.

The significantly higher interest of students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies when compared with those taught using conventional teaching strategy could be attributed to the fact that the use of games encourage participation and capture the interest of individuals in the learning process. This is why Selcuk and Keshin (2024) asserted that gamifications are used in order to engage students in interactive and immersive experiences designed to teach specific concepts, skills or subjects. Udoh and Ekon (2018) also added that teaching strategies plays an important role in the knowledge of a particular concept in science. This shows that when a learning task is set before the students, the aptness in responding to the said learning task is centrally controlled by interest. The extent to which the student will achieve in a particular

course of study is indicated by active participation in the study.

The findings on the difference among the mean achievement scores of Biology students taught human skeletal system using wordsearch, crossword and conventional teaching strategies also indicated a significant difference. Students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies had a significantly higher achievement when compared with those taught using conventional teaching strategy. A non-significant difference existed among the achievement mean scores of Biology students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies.

The significantly higher achievement of students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies when compared with those taught using conventional teaching strategy could be attributed to the fact that they encourage students to take active role in planning in the learning experience which could not be possible with the use of conventional teaching strategy. This is why Selcuk and Keshin (2024); Udo et al, (2024) asserted that the use of games engages students in interactive and immersive experiences. The finding of this study is in line with that of Ekon and Udoh (2021) who found that students taught Biology concept using innovative teaching methods had a significantly achievement than those taught the same concept with conventional teaching strategies. The findings also collaborate with Sambo and Sunday (2024) who found that there is a significant difference in the achievement of science students when taught with games. However, the findings disagree with Dinah (2022) who found no significant difference on students' achievement when taught with instructional strategies.

A non-significant difference existed between the achievement scores of students taught using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies. This could be attributed to the fact that the use of innovative teaching strategies

promotes conceptual change, motivation and excitement for enriching the learning human skeletal system resulting in enhancement of students' achievement. This is Selcuk and Keshin (2024) stated that gamification enhance learners' critical thinking skills making the learning of Biology concepts. The finding of the study is in line with Ekon and Udoh (2021) who showed that there was no significant difference between the achievement scores of students in senior secondary schools. However, the findings of the study disagree with the findings of Attah (2023) also found that that there was significant difference between the achievement scores of students in senior secondary schools with perception of difficult topics.

Conclusion

The use of wordsearch teaching strategy to teach human skeletal in Biology is as effective as the use of crossword teaching strategy in the achievement of Biology students. This is due to the fact that the lessons were interesting and the students were involved and carried along with appropriate teaching strategies. The study also showed that male and female students achieved equally when both genders were taught human skeletal using wordsearch and crossword teaching strategies.

Recommendations

1. Biology teachers should adopt gamification in teaching various concepts for effective engagement and provide fun ways to assess learning outcomes.
2. Parents and Biology teachers should encourage both male and female students towards excellence in Biology since they can benefit equally from science instructions depending on the engagement of an individual student.

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